

VARIATIONAL MECHANICS ANALYSIS OF THE STRESSES IN MICRODROP DEBOND SPECIMENS

Robert J. Scheer and John A. Nairn

Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Utah
Salt Lake City, Utah 84112, USA

ABSTRACT

A recently derived variational mechanics analysis of stresses in single-fiber model composites has been applied to the analysis of the stresses in the microdrop debond specimen. The new analysis is more accurate than the commonly applied shear-lag or elastic-plastic analyses. The results from a sample stress state calculation suggest that interfacial failure between the fiber and the microdrop is by mode I or opening mode failure at the beginning of the microdrop. The opening mode failure is caused by a large tensile radial stress at the fiber/matrix interface. Previous analyses of microdrop debond data have been in terms of a shear strength. We suggest that these analyses misrepresent microdrop debond results and recommend instead a failure analysis based on energy release rate and interfacial fracture toughness. A procedure for calculating the energy release rate for the growth of an interfacial crack is described.

KEYWORDS: Interface; Microdrop Debond Test; Interfacial Toughness; Single-Fiber Composites; Stress Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

To study the fiber matrix interface, many researchers have relied on single-fiber model composite tests. These tests include single-fiber fragmentation tests [1–15], fiber pull-out tests [16–18], microindentation tests [19], and microdrop debond tests [20]. The results of these various tests are significant, but the quantitative interpretation of the results has been limited by the near universal use of simplistic stress analyses such as shear-lag models [21–23] or elastic-plastic analyses [24]. A recent paper by Nairn [25] describes a new approach to the analysis of stresses in single-fiber model composites. The new analysis uses variational mechanics, achieves a closed-form solution, and is rigorously more accurate than previous analyses. In this paper we apply the variational analysis to the specific analysis of stresses in a microdrop debond specimen.

The geometry for the analysis of stresses in single fiber composites is shown in Fig. 1. The fiber is embedded in a cylinder of matrix. The stresses are axisymmetric and the presence of breaks or discontinuities in the fiber or matrix do not disturb the axial symmetry. The analysis in Ref. [25] makes only one assumption. It assumes σ_{zz} within each cylinder (fiber or matrix) depends only on the z

Figure 1: The two-cylinder model used for the axisymmetric stress analysis. A single fragment of length l showing the axial and radial coordinates in both dimensioned and dimensionless forms. B: A cross-section of the two-cylinder model showing the fiber of radius r_1 and the matrix of radius r_2 .

coordinate and is independent of the r coordinate. A general stress state that satisfies this assumption as well as stress equilibrium and traction boundary conditions is quoted from Ref. [25]. The stresses in the fiber are:

$$\sigma_{zz,1} = \psi \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{rz,1} = -\frac{\xi\psi'}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta,1} = \sigma_{rr,1} = \frac{\psi''}{4} \left(\xi^2 + \frac{\ln V_1}{V_2} \right) - \frac{\sigma_0}{2V_1} + \frac{\psi}{2} + \frac{V_2\eta}{V_1} \quad (3)$$

The stresses in the matrix are:

$$\sigma_{zz,2} = \frac{\sigma_0}{V_2} - \frac{V_1\psi}{V_2} \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_{rz,2} = \frac{V_1\psi'}{2V_2} \left(\xi - \frac{1}{\xi V_1} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{rr,2} = \frac{\psi''}{4V_2} (1 + \ln \xi^2 V_1 - \xi^2 V_1) + \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{2V_2} - \frac{V_1\psi}{2V_2} - \eta \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\xi^2 V_1} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta,2} = \frac{\psi''}{4V_2} (1 + \ln \xi^2 V_1 - \xi^2 V_1) + \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{2V_2} - \frac{V_1\psi}{2V_2} - \eta \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\xi^2 V_1} \right) \quad (7)$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the volume fractions of the fiber and the matrix, σ_0 is the total axial stress applied in the z direction, ξ is a dimensionless radial coordinate defined by $\xi = \frac{r}{r_1}$, and the applied radial stress is zero. The stresses are defined in terms of an unknown function $\psi(\zeta)$, where ζ is a dimensionless axial coordinate defined by $\zeta = \frac{z}{r_1}$, and an undetermined constant η . By axial symmetry, the unspecified shear stresses are all zero.

Figure 2: A matrix microdrop of dimensionless length 2ρ . A: The microdrop specimen. B: An idealized microdrop specimen showing the boundary conditions relevant to the microdrop debond test. σ_f is the background fiber tensile stress. σ_m is the stress applied to the microdrop during the test.

The stresses in Eqs. (1)–(7) constitute an admissible stress state. By the principles of variational mechanics, the best approximation to the true stress state is found by finding the $\psi(\zeta)$ and η that minimize the total complementary energy. A calculus of variations analysis leads to a fourth order Euler equation for $\psi(\zeta)$ [25]:

$$\psi^{iv} + p_1 \psi'' + p_2 \psi = p_3 \sigma_0 + p_4 T + p_5 \langle \psi \rangle$$

where $T = T_s - T_0$ is the difference between the sample temperature and the stress-free temperature and the constants p_i depend on the mechanical properties of the fiber and the matrix. The constants are defined in the Appendix. The constant η is defined in terms of $\psi(\zeta)$ by

$$\eta = -\frac{C_{12}\sigma_0 + D_2 T + C_{23}\langle \psi \rangle}{C_{22}} \quad (8)$$

where $\langle \psi \rangle$ is the average value of $\psi(\zeta)$ [25]

MICRODROP SPECIMEN ANALYSIS

A typical microdrop debond specimen with a microdrop of length l and dimensionless length 2ρ ($\rho = \frac{l}{2r_1}$) is shown in Fig. 2A. A pair of knife edges contact the matrix microdrop near the fiber and the fiber is pulled until the interface fails [20]. We idealize the nearly elliptical microdrop by replacing it with a cylinder. The length of the cylinder is chosen to match the length of the microdrop. The radius of the cylinder is chosen to preserve the effective volume fraction of the fiber within the microdrop. The idealized microdrop specimen analysis coordinates are shown in Fig. 2B. σ_m is the compressive stress applied to the matrix microdrop; σ_f is the initial background fiber stress that may be negligible; the total applied axial stress is $\sigma_0 = V_1 \sigma_f$.

As shown in Fig. 2B, the microdrop debond test boundary conditions are

$$\psi(\rho) = \sigma_f - \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{V_2} \quad \psi(-\rho) = \sigma_f \quad \psi'(\pm\rho) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Using these boundary conditions, the solution to Eq. (8) is

$$\psi = \psi_0 (1 - \phi) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\psi_0 = \frac{p_3 \sigma_0 + p_4 T}{p_2 - p_5} \quad (11)$$

and the new function ϕ has two possible forms. When $p_1^2 - 4p_2 < 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi = & \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{\psi_0} + \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \frac{2h_2'(\rho) \cosh \alpha \zeta \cos \beta \zeta - 2h_1'(\rho) \sinh \alpha \zeta \sin \beta \zeta + \frac{\gamma}{\rho} (\cosh 2\alpha\rho - \cos 2\beta\rho)}{\beta \sinh 2\alpha\rho + \alpha \sin 2\beta\rho + \frac{\gamma}{\rho} (\cosh 2\alpha\rho - \cos 2\beta\rho)} \\ & + \left(\frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \frac{2h_4'(\rho) \sinh \alpha \zeta \cos \beta \zeta - 2h_3'(\rho) \cosh \alpha \zeta \sin \beta \zeta}{\beta \sinh 2\alpha\rho - \alpha \sin 2\beta\rho} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(\rho) = \cosh \alpha\rho \cos \beta\rho & \quad h_3(\rho) = \sinh \alpha\rho \cos \beta\rho & \quad \alpha = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2\sqrt{p_2} - p_1} \\ h_2(\rho) = \sinh \alpha\rho \sin \beta\rho & \quad h_4(\rho) = \cosh \alpha\rho \sin \beta\rho & \quad \beta = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2\sqrt{p_2} + p_1} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

When $p_1^2 - 4p_2 > 0$

$$\phi = \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{\psi_0} + \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \frac{\frac{\beta \cosh \alpha \zeta}{\sinh \alpha \rho} - \frac{\alpha \cosh \beta \zeta}{\sinh \beta \rho} - \frac{2\gamma}{\rho}}{\beta \coth \alpha\rho - \alpha \coth \beta\rho - \frac{2\gamma}{\rho}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \frac{\frac{\beta \sinh \alpha \zeta}{\cosh \alpha \rho} - \frac{\alpha \sinh \beta \zeta}{\cosh \beta \rho}}{\beta \tanh \alpha\rho - \alpha \tanh \beta\rho} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\alpha = \sqrt{-\frac{p_1}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{p_1^2}{4} - p_2}} \quad \beta = \sqrt{-\frac{p_1}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{p_1^2}{4} - p_2}} \quad (15)$$

In Eqs. (12) and (14), the new term γ is defined by

$$\gamma = \frac{p_5}{p_2 - p_5} \sqrt{1 - \frac{p_1^2}{4p_2}} \quad (16)$$

We substitute the results for ψ into Eq. (8) and find an explicit expression for the constant η . The result is

$$\eta = \eta_0 + \frac{C_{23} \psi_0 \langle \phi \rangle}{C_{22}} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\eta_0 = -\frac{C_{12} \sigma_0 + D_2 T + C_{23} \psi_0}{C_{22}} = \frac{p_8 \sigma_0 + p_9 T}{p_2 - p_5} \quad (18)$$

and p_8 and p_9 are defined in the Appendix. The average value of ϕ is easily evaluated. When $p_1^2 - 4p_2 < 0$, the result is:

$$\langle \phi \rangle = \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{\psi_0} + \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \left(\frac{C_{22} C_{33}}{C_{23}^2}\right) \frac{\frac{\gamma}{\rho} (\cosh 2\alpha\rho - \cos 2\beta\rho)}{\beta \sinh 2\alpha\rho + \alpha \sin 2\beta\rho + \frac{\gamma}{\rho} (\cosh 2\alpha\rho - \cos 2\beta\rho)} \quad (19)$$

When $p_1^2 - 4p_2 > 0$, the result is:

$$\langle \phi \rangle = -\left(1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{\psi_0} + \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{2V_1 \psi_0}\right) \left(\frac{C_{22} C_{33}}{C_{23}^2}\right) \frac{\frac{2\gamma}{\rho}}{\beta \coth \alpha\rho - \alpha \coth \beta\rho - \frac{2\gamma}{\rho}} \quad (20)$$

As shown in Ref. [25], the constants ψ_0 and η_0 define the stress state far from the sample ends. In other words, setting $\psi(\zeta) = \psi_0$ and $\eta = \eta_0$ and substituting in Eqs. (1)–(7) gives the stresses in two infinitely long concentric cylinders. Because the one assumption of σ_{zz} being independent of r is correct for infinitely long cylinders, the resulting stress state is exact. By Eq. (10), we see that ϕ defines the fraction deviation from the far-field stress state. ϕ will vary most near the sample ends and approach zero far from the sample ends. If the microdrop is not very long, however, ϕ will not reach zero before encroaching on the opposite end of the microdrop.

Once we know ψ and η we can calculate the total strain energy in the microdrop using

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \bar{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{K} \bar{\sigma} dV \quad (21)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor and \mathbf{K} is the compliance tensor. The result is [26]:

$$U = 2\rho\pi r_1^3 [C_{11}\sigma_0^2 + (C_{13}\sigma_0 - D_3T)\langle\psi\rangle + (C_{12}\sigma_0 - D_2T)\eta] \quad (22)$$

SAMPLE STRESS STATE

A microdrop debond experiment begins with a fiber and microdrop under little or no load ($\sigma_f = 0$ or σ_f small). The knife edges are placed near the microdrop and the fiber is pulled. The pulling will put compressive stress on the matrix and the magnitude of σ_m will increase as the fiber is pulled. For a sample calculation we pick a low value of σ_f ($\sigma_f = 10$ MPa) and set σ_m to -100 MPa. To include thermal stresses we pick a typical T of -125°C . Lastly, we pick fiber volume fraction and microdrop length. Typical experimental results have $V_1 = 5\%$ and length = 10 fiber diameters or about $80 \mu\text{m}$ when using graphite fibers [27]. The fiber and matrix properties used are listed in the Appendix. The far-field stress constants for $\sigma_0 = V_1\sigma_f = 0.5$ MPa and $T = -125^\circ\text{C}$ are $\psi_0 = -300$ MPa and $\eta_0 = 7.57$ MPa. The far-field fiber stress is compressive due to axial thermal shrinkage of the microdrop relative to the fiber. The far-field radial stress at the fiber/matrix interface is

$$\sigma_{rr,1}(1) (\text{far field}) = -\frac{\sigma_0}{2V_1} + \frac{\psi_0}{2} + \frac{V_2\eta_0}{V_1} = -11.1 \text{ MPa} \quad (23)$$

The radial stress is compressive due to a shrink-fit of the matrix around the fiber caused by radial thermal contraction of the matrix.

The stresses that result from the assumed loading conditions in the previous paragraph are given in Fig. 3. The x axis plots distance from the knife edges in units of fiber diameters. The axial fiber tensile stress at the knife edges is

$$\sigma_{zz,1}(\zeta = +\rho) = \sigma_f - \frac{V_2\sigma_m}{V_1} = 1910 \text{ MPa} \quad (24)$$

It decreases in about three fiber diameters to a plateau value of about 560 MPa. Near the end of the microdrop, $\sigma_{zz,1}$ decreases again in about three fiber diameters to the boundary value of 10 MPa. It is significant that the plateau value differs from the far-field fiber stress value of ψ_0 . A 10 fiber diameter microdrop is short and the far-field stress state is not approached. If the microdrop was longer (say 1000 fiber diameters) the fiber stress would be nearly equal to ψ_0 at positions more than several fiber diameters from either end.

The interfacial shear stress is zero on both ends of the microdrop as required by boundary conditions. Near the knife edges $\tau_{rz}(1)$ peaks at -257 MPa and then returns to zero all in about three fiber diameters. The form of the shear stresses differs significantly from that predicted by simplistic models [21–24]. The simplistic models predict a maximum shear stress at the two ends of the microdrop. A

Figure 3: The fiber axial stress, interfacial shear stress and interfacial radial stress in a microdrop specimen. The horizontal line labeled ψ_0 is the far-field fiber axial stress. The distance axis is distance from the knife edges. The compressive stress applied to the matrix is -100 MPa; the background fiber stress is 10 MPa; the total microdrop length is 10 fiber diameters.

peak shear stress at the microdrop ends violates boundary conditions and results in an inadmissible stress state [28].

The interfacial radial stress is tensile and peaks at 1395 MPa near the knife edge. The radial tensile stress is caused by the matrix compressive stress and differential Poisson's contraction between the fiber and matrix [29]. The radial stress decreases to a plateau value of about -38 MPa. The plateau value is similar in magnitude but more compressive than the far-field radial compressive stress. Near the end of the microdrop, $\sigma_{rr,1}(l)$ decreases to a compressive stress peak of -616 MPa.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

The goal of microdrop debond test is to characterize the quality of the fiber/matrix interface. The experimental observable is the force required to dislodge the microdrop from the fiber; *i.e.* the force required to break the interface. Previous microdrop debond experiments used a simplistic analysis (*e.g.* elastic plastic analysis [24]) and calculated an interfacial shear strength using

$$\tau = \frac{F}{2\pi r_1 l} \quad (25)$$

In Eq. (25), F is the failure force and l is the length of the microdrop. In terms of the stresses used in this paper, Eq. (25) becomes

$$\tau = \frac{r_1}{2l} \left(\sigma_f - \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{V_1} \right) \quad (26)$$

For a specimen that would fail under the stress example in Fig. 3 we would calculate $\tau = 48$ MPa.

It is difficult to imagine what feature of the stress state in Fig. 3 corresponds to a shear strength of 48 MPa. Close inspection of the stress state further suggests that interfacial failure may not even be a shear failure. The largest interfacial stress is the radial stress. The maximum radial stress occurs at the point of contact with the knife edges. A likely failure mechanism is mode I or opening mode fracture initiating at the knife edges. If, as suggested, the peak force in the microdrop debond experiment

Figure 4: An idealized matrix microdrop specimen of dimensionless length 2ρ having an interfacial crack of dimensionless length 2δ emanating for the top of the microdrop. Region I is the cracked region above the dashed line. Region II is the uncracked region below the dashed line.

corresponds to tensile failure of the interface, it is inappropriate to use Eq. (25) and claim to be measuring an interfacial shear strength.

It is tempting to calculate the maximum radial tensile stress using the analysis of this paper and equate that with an interfacial tensile strength. Due to the complex nature of the stress state, however, this approach is probably an oversimplification. We recommend a fracture mechanics analysis based on the energy release rate for crack growth of interfacial failure beginning at the knife edges. A post failure stress analysis is illustrated in Fig. 4. The originally intact microdrop specimen now has a crack of length a or dimensionless length 2δ where $\delta = \frac{a}{2r_1}$.

The stress analysis of the cracked sample involves finding the stresses in region I, the region near the cracked interface, and the stresses in region II, the remainder of the microdrop. Because the radial stress is tensile before failure, the crack should open and result in stress free fracture surfaces. A zero shear stress on the crack surface and Eq. (2) implies that $\psi' = 0$ or that ψ is constant. By the boundary

conditions in Eq. (9), the ψ function in region I is

$$\psi_I(\zeta) = \sigma_f - \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{V_1} \quad (27)$$

On the fracture surface the radial stress is also zero. This constraint and Eq. (3) result in

$$\eta_I = \frac{\sigma_m}{2}$$

Given $\psi_I(\zeta)$ and η_I , the stresses in region I are completely determined. Integrating the strain energy, the total strain energy in region I is

$$U_I = 2\delta\pi r_1^3 \left[\frac{\left(\sigma_f - \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{V_1}\right)^2}{2E_A} + \frac{V_2 \sigma_m^2}{2V_1 E_m} \right] \quad (28)$$

At the top of region II, the boundary conditions are identical to the microdrop boundary conditions in Eq. (9). In region II the stresses are thus the stresses that exist in a microdrop of dimensionless length $2(\rho - \delta)$. From Eq. (22), the strain energy in region II is

$$U_{II} = 2(\rho - \delta)\pi r_1^3 [C_{11}\sigma_0^2 + (C_{13}\sigma_0 - D_3T)\langle\psi\rangle + (C_{12}\sigma_0 - D_2T)\eta] \quad (29)$$

The total strain energy in the cracked microdrop specimen is thus $U = U_I + U_{II}$ or

$$U = 2\pi r_1^3 \left(\delta \left[\frac{\left(\sigma_f - \frac{\sigma_m V_2}{V_1}\right)^2}{2E_A} + \frac{V_2 \sigma_m^2}{2V_1 E_m} \right] + (\rho - \delta) [C_{11}\sigma_0^2 + (C_{13}\sigma_0 - D_3T)\langle\psi\rangle + (C_{12}\sigma_0 - D_2T)\eta] \right) \quad (30)$$

The energy release rate for the initiation and growth of an interface crack can be calculated from the total strain energy using

$$G = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \Big|_{\text{const. disp.}} = -\frac{1}{4\pi r_1^2} \frac{\partial U}{\partial \delta} \Big|_{\text{const. disp.}} \quad (31)$$

where $A = 2\pi r_1 a = 4\pi r_1^2 \delta$ is the fracture area associated with an interface crack of length a . In a fracture mechanics model of interfacial failure we assume that the interface crack will propagate when the energy release rate for interfacial crack growth exceeds the interfacial fracture toughness. The evaluation of G using Eq. (31) is a non-trivial problem. It is complicated by the requirement of differentiating at constant displacement and the presence of residual thermal stresses. The energy release rate calculation will be the subject of a future publication [26].

APPENDIX

In Ref. [25], the complementary energy was expressed in terms of constants that depend on the sample dimensions and on the mechanical properties of the fiber and the matrix:

$$C_{11} = \frac{1}{4V_1^2} \left[\frac{1 - \nu_T}{E_T} + \frac{4V_1(1 - \nu_m)}{V_2 E_m} + \frac{1 + \nu_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (A1)$$

$$C_{33} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1 - \nu_T}{E_T} + \frac{2(1 - 2\nu_A)}{E_A} + \frac{4V_1(1 - \nu_m)}{V_2 E_m} + \frac{1 + \nu_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (A2)$$

$$C_{35} = \frac{1}{16} \left[\left(1 + 2\frac{\ln V_1}{V_2}\right) \left(\frac{1 - \nu_T}{E_T} - \frac{2\nu_A}{E_A}\right) + \left(\frac{2V_1}{V_2} \left(1 + \frac{\ln V_1}{V_2}\right) + 1\right) \frac{1 - 3\nu_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (A3)$$

$$C_{55} = \frac{1 - \nu_T}{48E_T} \left[1 + \frac{3\ln V_1}{V_2} + 3 \left(\frac{\ln V_1}{V_2}\right)^2 \right] + \frac{1 - \nu_m}{96E_m} \left[\frac{5 - V_1 + 2V_1^2}{V_2 V_1} + \frac{6V_1 \ln V_1}{V_2^2} - \frac{6(\ln V_1)^2}{V_2^2} \right] \quad (A4)$$

$$C_{44} = \frac{1}{16} \left[\frac{1}{G_A} - \frac{1}{G_m} \left(1 + \frac{2}{V_2} + \frac{2 \ln V_1}{V_2^2} \right) \right] \quad (A5)$$

$$C_{22} = \frac{V_2}{V_1} \left[\frac{V_2(1-\nu_T)}{V_1 E_T} + \frac{1-\nu_m}{E_m} + \frac{1+\nu_m}{V_1 E_m} \right] \quad (A6)$$

$$C_{23} = \frac{1}{2V_1} \left[\frac{V_2(1-\nu_T)}{E_T} - \frac{2V_2\nu_A}{E_A} + \frac{2V_1(1-\nu_m)}{E_m} + \frac{V_2(1+\nu_m)}{E_m} \right] \quad (A7)$$

$$C_{13} = -\frac{1}{4V_1} \left[\frac{1-\nu_T}{E_T} - \frac{2\nu_A}{E_A} + \frac{4V_1(1-\nu_m)}{V_2 E_m} + \frac{1+\nu_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (A8)$$

$$D_3 = \frac{1}{2} [\alpha_T + \alpha_A - 2\alpha_m] \quad (A9)$$

$$C_{12} = -\frac{V_2}{2V_1^2} \left[\frac{1-\nu_T}{E_T} + \frac{2V_1(1-\nu_m)}{V_2 E_m} + \frac{1+\nu_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (A10)$$

$$D_2 = \frac{V_2}{V_1} [\alpha_T - \alpha_m] \quad (A11)$$

In these equations, E_A and E_T are the axial and transverse tensile moduli of the fiber, G_A is the axial shear modulus of the fiber, ν_A and ν_T are the axial and transverse Poisson's ratios of the fiber, and E_m , G_m , and ν_m are the tensile modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio of the matrix. The constants in Eq. (8) and in Eq. (18) are:

$$p_1 = \frac{2C_{35} - C_{44}}{C_{55}} \quad p_2 = \frac{C_{33}}{C_{55}} \quad p_3 = \frac{C_{23}C_{12} - C_{22}C_{13}}{C_{22}C_{55}} \quad (A12)$$

$$p_4 = \frac{C_{23}D_2 - C_{22}D_3}{C_{22}C_{55}} \quad p_5 = \frac{C_{23}^2}{C_{22}C_{55}} \quad (A13)$$

$$p_8 = \frac{C_{23}C_{13} - C_{33}C_{12}}{C_{22}C_{55}} \quad p_9 = \frac{C_{23}D_3 - C_{33}D_2}{C_{22}C_{55}} \quad (A14)$$

The sample stress state calculated in this paper is for a typical epoxy microdrop on a graphite fiber. We assumed the following properties for the fiber and matrix:

$$E_A = 220000 \text{ MPa}$$

$$E_T = 14000 \text{ MPa}$$

$$G_A = 35000 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\nu_A = 0.20$$

$$\nu_T = 0.35$$

$$\alpha_A = -0.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$$

$$\alpha_T = 18.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$$

$$E_m = 4300 \text{ MPa}$$

$$G_m = \frac{E_m}{2(1+\nu_m)} = 1604 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\nu_m = 0.34$$

$$\alpha_m = -0.36 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$$

(A15)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported in part by a contract from NASA Langley Research Center (NAS1-18833) monitored by Dr. John Crews and in part by a gift from E. I. duPont deNemours & Company monitored by Dr. Alan R. Wedgewood. We also thank Dr. James Jakubowski of DOW Chemical for supplying typical experimental results.

REFERENCES

1. N. J. Wadsworth and I. Spilling, Brit. J. Appl. Phys. (J. Phys. D.), 1, 1049 (1968).
2. A. A. Fraser, F. H. Ancker and A. T. DiBenedetto, Proc. 30th Conf. SPI Reinforced Plastics Div., Section 22-A, 1 (1975).
3. T. Ohsawa, A. Nakayama, M. Miwa and A. Hesegawa, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 22, 3203 (1978).

4. W. A. Fraser, F. H Ancker, A. T. DiBenedetto and B. Elbirli, Polym. Comp., **4**, 238 (1983).
5. L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich, J. D. Camping and W. J. Park, Proc.35th Conf. SPI Reinforced Plastics Div., Section 20-C, 1 (1980).
6. L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich and P. F Lloyd, J. Adhesion, **16**, 1 (1982).
7. L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich, M. F Koenig and P. F. Lloyd, J. Adhesion, **16**, 133 (1983).
8. L. T. Drzal, M. J. Rich and M. F. Koenig, J. Adhesion, **18**, 49 (1985).
9. M. J. Rich and L. T. Drzal, Proc. 41st Conf. SPI Reinforced Plastics Div., Section 2-F, 1 (1986).
10. W. D. Bascom and R. M Jensen., J. Adhesion, **19**, 219 (1986).
11. M. J. Folkes and W. K. Wong, Polymer, **28**, 1309 (1987).
12. L. DiLandro and M. Pegoraro, J. Mat. Sci., **22**, 1980 (1987).
13. L. DiLandro, A. T. DiBenedetto and J. Groeger, Polymer Composites, **9**, 209 (1988).
14. A. T. DiBenedetto and P. J. Lex, Polymer Composites, **29**, 543 (1989).
15. A. N. Netravali, P. Schwartz and S. L. Phoenix, Polymer Composites, **10**, 385 (1989).
16. M. R. Piggot, P. S. Chua and D. Andison, Polymer Composites, **6**, 242 (1985).
17. M. R. Piggot, Comp. Sci. & Tech., **30**, 295 (1987).
18. L. S. Penn, F. A. Bystry and H. J. Marchionni, Polymer Composites, **4**, 26 (1983).
19. J. F. Mandell, E. J. H. Chen and F. J. McGarry, Intl. J. Adhes. Adhes., **1**, 40 (1980).
20. U. Gaur and B. Miller, Comp. Sci. & Tech., **34**, 35 (1989).
21. H. L. Cox, Brit.J. Appl. Phys., **3**, 72 (1952).
22. B. W. Rosen, in: Fiber Composite Materials, American Society of Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, 1964, Chap. 3, p. 37.
23. J. Amirbayat and W. S. Hearle, Fiber Sci. and Tech., **2**, 123 (1969).
24. A. Kelly and W. R. Tyson, J.Mech. Phys. Solids, **10**, 199 (1963).
25. J. A. Nairn, Mechanics of Materials, submitted (1990).
26. J. A. Nairn and R. J. Scheer, unpublished results (1991).
27. J. Jakubowski, personal communication (1990).
28. J. M. Whitney and L. T. Drzal, Toughened Composites, ASTM STP 937, 179 (1987).
29. L. J. Broutman and F. J. McGarry, Modern Plastics, **40**, 161 (1962).